

THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN ONTOGENESIS AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN ADOLESCENT PERIOD

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Abstract. *This article states that human creativity is a unique feature of thinking, that it is an important condition for a person to find his place in society, self-awareness, socialization, especially for young people in early adolescence, so that they can foresee their future life. plans analyzed by the recognition of foreign and domestic scientists that this is an important and pressing issue for young people today to find the right path in their lives.*

Keywords: *behavior, intelligence, heuristic abilities, creativity, cognitive, early adolescence, empathy, social role, values, cognitive process.*

Realization of the need for personal development in the conditions of modern technological changes, socio-cultural contradictions in the world, the near, medium and long perspectives, goals that determine his life activities and behavior, as well as spiritual values for society, nature and himself - is based on determining one's moral attitude and determining one's purpose in life, creative self-awareness and continuous self-improvement. It is known that the influence of creativity in self-expression with the formation of a life strategy often helps people to engage in a certain scientific or practical activity in the future, and that is why it is of urgent importance.

According to this year's scientific forecasts of the "International Labor Organization", the number of unemployed people in the world has exceeded 205 million, and it can be recognized that these indicators may increase even more in 2024. The question of the impact of creativity on the life-strategic self-awareness of young people is constantly relevant and will remain relevant in the future.

The development of a person's creative abilities can continue during an important period of his life, but there are optimal sensitive age periods for their formation in ontogeny. It is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of students when organizing educational activities that help to develop intellectual and heuristic abilities.

E.Gaziyev noted that the formation of individual characteristics proves that it occurs in the process of age development, and much depends on what is obtained from psychic characteristics that serve as guidance in different periods of childhood, to what extent the characteristics of age and the characteristics of the mind affect. Although it is never too late to learn, there are strict age restrictions for the development of thinking.

Three ideas can be distinguished regarding the development of creativity in ontogeny. According to the first, there is a gradual continuous growth of creativity with age. Supporters of the second point out that a child's creativity decreases with education. Scientists who adhere to the third point of view defend the idea of the changing nature of the development of creativity.

E.Torrance was the first to be interested in the issue of periods of decline and growth during the development of creativity [4]. According to him, the peaks of creativity development correspond to preschool age (5 years old), junior school age, early adolescence and high school

age (9, 13, 17 years old). Thus, approximately every four years, we can observe an increase in the development of creativity.

According to geneticists, men are carriers of developing characteristics, and women are carriers of conservative characteristics[5]. Accordingly, with the condition that the average values are equal, the variation of any characteristics of men is greater than that of women. Many researchers believe that the differences in the creative abilities of men and women are partly related to the development of mental abilities. Women perform better on tests of the speed of registration of objects of the same category, they develop fine motor skills better. Men perform better on spatial tests. This applies primarily to tasks that require spatial perception and a creative approach.

E. Goziev found that gender differences in performing creative and other spatial thinking tasks exist in children even before puberty [6]. It is known that sex hormones affect differences in the organic development of the brain from an early age (many data confirm that the thoughts of 8-9-year-old boys are better oriented in space).

Differences in the role of the front and back sections of the cerebral cortex, as well as the right and left hemispheres of the brain have been identified in men and women [7, pp. 155-158]. According to psychologists, creativity includes independent behavior and the creation of a unique, unique, individual and creative personality. Such independent behavior is more common in men than in women.

As stated by L.S. Vygotsky, "the norm of creative children's development is a characteristic feature of the character of adolescents of the early years, where the inner desire for creativity and the inner tendency to productivity are embodied." is a characteristic feature of the dental period" [8, pp. 10-12]. But the understanding of creativity is not limited to its compensatory function in human life. That is, creative mechanisms are directly related to the cognitive processes of a person. A number of criteria are used when a person tries to determine the basis of creativity. They are represented by the following aspects (Table 1).

Creative criteria are not "new" in themselves, but "a new use of something previously known", that is, the search for other methods of application, not certain ways of solving old problems (because the spiritual people with diseases are able to produce new things).

The process of creating new personal things and improving existing objects reveals the social role and importance of empathy, without which a new result cannot be achieved. In this case, in order to discover new things in the subject, the object must appear in front of the subject from a new point of view, or the subject must move in space and time and gain a new point of view.

In our opinion, one of the components of creative action can be empathy as a way of knowing another person, his thoughts, feelings, ways of expressing internal components.

"Empathy" means "the ability to imagine oneself in the place of another person, to understand his feelings, desires, ideas and actions" [9, p. 187]. Empathy as a personality trait is closely related to the concept of creativity, and sometimes works as one of the means of its implementation. The essence of empathy is found in the modeling of the "I" in the model of any event or other person and consists of an imaginary "I".

We believe that empathy works as a tool to access the creative process of the individual.

The imaginary "I" is formed as a result of the transition of different images from the nomen system to another system. As a result, the image acquires the functional status of "I". Images of other people (real or imaginary - acting) and images of other objects, including inanimate ones, can merge with imaginary "I-images" with which the real "I" of a person identifies himself [10, p. 57].

In order for a creative product to appear, it is necessary to stand in the position of the imaginary "I" in the creative act itself. In our opinion, such a mechanism of the creative process is carried out by the individual. In other words, a new look at familiar things should be provided by the creator, the ability of a person to get out of the usual, familiar framework of solving this or that task, to approach it in a new way.

A person's creativity is manifested due to the social component. In fact, as a social being, a person is capable of various creative actions that are directly determined by society.

Psychologist A.A. Odiljonova said that "the social component encourages a person to create new things, to reconsider the existing material and spiritual objects of culture. This explains the need for creative abilities of the individual as a need of society" [11, p. 35].

In our opinion, values are manifested in certain actions, the purpose of which is independence of thoughts and actions, the main values of a creative person are expressed in free choice and protection of the interests required by society. Note that, in this context, self-determination and openness to change are significantly associated with creativity, while tradition and security values are negatively associated with creativity.

In modern psychological-pedagogical research, the problem of the influence of creativity on the development of gender differences becomes especially relevant in the context of the construction of society, because it is in culture that the concept of male and female psychology was developed. Opinions about gender differences in creativity among early adolescents and the influence of age on the development of creativity often differ.

E. Ghaziyev in his monograph devoted to the problem of psychology of ontogenesis, "Early adolescence occupies a special place in the maturation of the human personality. It is an important stage of human development. In the period of early adolescence, psychological changes of great importance take place, and under the influence of education and training necessary for the further development of the child in certain social life conditions, stable, strong, positive qualities are formed. Psychological changes that are gradually emerging, the qualities that are formed and the growth of the personality, first of all, the activities of boys and girls of this age (leading and auxiliary activities: study, work and play are meant) is directly related to the feature. He admitted that "adolescents of early age have their own characteristics, which are different from other youth periods, and they are expressed in emotional and willful qualities" [9, p. 146].

As a young adolescent matures, new qualities and qualities begin to appear in his mental world, and a sharp restructuring takes place in his psyche. "Changes put new demands on him, which, in turn, require him to be given more rights and freedom, first of all, to come to an

independent decision and implement his behavior considering it acceptable. Mental improvement, striving for perfection, relative stability are the most important features of early adolescence" [9, p. 58].

It is known that early adolescence is a period of formation of worldview, belief, point of view, position, self-awareness, evaluation, etc. "If a child of elementary school age acts according to the instructions of adults or his random, involuntary wishes, a teenager of the first age begins to organize his activities on the basis of certain principles, beliefs and personal views" [12, page 150]. According to D. I. Feldstein, social development during early adolescence precedes intellectual development and determines the possibility of transitioning to a new stage of individual development in ontogenesis [13, p. 150]. It is at this age that the transition from childhood to adulthood occurs. The characteristic features of the process of personality formation are the striving for self-knowledge, self-awareness, as well as changing the content of the motivational complex. These changes have a significant impact on the substantive side of thinking, that is, on the development of creativity.

During this period, the child realizes himself as an adult and revises his value system. It determines the direction and content of the activity of the adolescent, his new aspirations, wishes, and experiences. At this time, stable forms of behavior, character traits, and emotional tools are formed. This is a period of rapid accumulation of achievements, knowledge, skills, formation of "I", gaining a new social position. The main neoplasms of the adolescent personality are associated with changes in the type of leading activity and relationships. In this period, the driving force is the resolution of internal conflicts that arise in connection with the active interaction of the adolescent in the social environment.

A characteristic feature of the social situation of early adolescent development is that he enters a new system of communication with adults and peers, takes a new place among them and performs new functions. This period, more than any other period, depends on the reality of the environment, because it is at this age that the child's perception of the world, anxiety and psychological discomfort appear, and the early adolescent dreams of his privileges. Such a situation is helped by subjective impressions: sudden physiological changes, dreams and ideals, crisis conflicts with oneself and family, a feeling of loneliness and a desire to reach the status of adults as soon as possible.

In his research, D. Feldstein defines the period of early adolescence as "a separate stage of mental development, a stage of transition from childhood to adulthood, with specific mental development characteristics and a sensitive type of leading activity, which is socially useful for young people" [14, pp. 3–9], admits that.

Based on the recognitions of the above-mentioned authors, in our opinion, an adolescent of early age can work with concepts, hypotheses, planning research activities and a large amount of information due to the development of conceptual, linguistic-logical and abstract thinking. This happens in the conditions of active development of cognitive, emotional and volitional processes that jointly stimulate the mental activity of an early-age teenager. Mental processes that form images of the environment are called cognitive mental processes.

"The development of cognitive processes of early adolescents (emotions, perception, thinking, memory, emotions, attention, etc.), the formation of complex thinking mechanisms of analytical and synthetic activity, the transition to abstract, theoretical thinking, the development of thinking deductive forms, the ability to draw conclusions, is determined by the development of

hypothetical and hypothetical thinking" [15, p. 98]. The dynamics of this development, the lack of formation of certain processes and mechanisms of thinking cause a number of difficulties of early adolescence, which are repeated both in education and in other areas of early adolescent life [13].

Unresolved life plans and tasks lead to the formation of an inadequate personality in the early adolescent generation. Including:

abandoning psychological closeness, avoiding close interpersonal relationships with others;

indifference to time limits or intervals, inability to make life plans, fear of becoming an adult, fear of change;

production, dispersion of creative abilities, inability to mobilize internal resources and focus on one main activity;

forming a "negative identity", rejecting self-determination and choosing negative role models.

In other studies, a number of stages of identity development determined by the level of professional, religious and political self-determination of early adolescents have been identified:

- "undefined identity" (the person has not yet clearly formed, has not chosen beliefs, profession and has not faced the problem of identity crisis);

- "early identification" (a person has already joined a certain system of relationships, but not by his own will, as a result of the crisis and trials he experienced, but based on the opinion of others, under the influence of example or authority);

- "moratorium" (a person is in the process of a normative crisis of self-determination and chooses the only option that can be considered his own from many options);

- "mature person" (the crisis of self-determination is over, the person has moved from self-searching to practical self-awareness).

During early adolescence, the final formation of the ontogenesis lines of the life world takes place. First of all, they are expressed by the choice of worldview, moral and professional self-determination. When deciding the issue of professional self-determination, choosing a life path, a teenager of the first age begins to move from basic life positions, beliefs, ideals, to value directions.

Both generalized feelings and relatively stable experiences (intellectual, moral, aesthetic, etc.) develop. However, during early adolescence, we observe the process of hiding creative qualities in the form of introversion. This happens for a number of reasons:

- social and personal restrictions;

- fear of self-discovery;

- the negative attitude of the environment to personal early adolescent manifestations.

The development of creativity in early adolescence becomes an important stage for the further development of a person, his self-expression, which helps to adapt to adult society.

Summary. Based on the above recognition and opinions, we can come to the following conclusions:

1. Creativity is important for the development of a person's theory of self-awareness. Self-awareness refers to the balanced and harmonious development of a person through the use of adequate efforts aimed at revealing the genetic, individual and personal potential.

2. The stability and adequacy of the process and result of self-awareness is related to the strategies used for self-awareness. In the self-realization strategy of early adolescents, we are

guided by the process of self-realization of the individual, his life meaning and value orientations, based on long-sighted plans and forecasts. we recognize.

3. Learning to choose self-awareness and implementation strategies requires consideration of two aspects:

- firstly, it includes meaningful, value-semantic and motivational formations, as well as the nature of self-management of a person;

- secondly, the focus of the individual's self-awareness, as a focused basis for the selection of appropriate strategies, including components such as semantic and temporal perspective, personality orientation, self-attitude and subjective control.

4. The choice of a strategy of self-realization is carried out in conditions of uncertainty, its elimination primarily depends on the specific aspects of creative characteristics.

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